

Deliverable 3.2

MVP Analytics Tools Module

Work Package: WP3. Technical development and repurposing of games

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Abstract (for public dissemination only)	This document describes the Minimum Viable Platforms Analytics Module developed for GREAT to get an overview of the running case studies, and easily make data accessible for analysis for all partners.
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Table 1: GANTT chart of WP3 for D3.2

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List of Abbreviations

CA / GA	Consortium Agreement / Grant Agreement
CI	Continuous Integration
CD	Continuous Development
CO	Confidential
DMP	Data Management Plan
DeLA	Data-enriched Learning Analytics
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EMB	Executive Management Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulations
GREAT	Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation
H2020	Horizon 2020 program of the European Union
Live Ops	Live Operations where you can easily track data (e.g visual dashboard)
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
PMC	Project Management Committee
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SC	Scientific Committee
TRL	Technology Readiness Level (1= low / 9=high)
UKRI	United Kingdom Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

This document describes the Minimum Viable Analytics (MVP) Module that combines data sources from the proprietary technology platforms DiBL and PlayMob. The Analytics Module is the realisation of what was specified in [D3.1](#), where most of the features envisioned are available in the MVP. This can be summarised in the following:

- Ensure collected data is organised in a sufficiently segmented way for later analysis.
- Create tools to monitor recent data quality/volume to validate data collection.
- Share access to the data in a suitable format for in depth analysis.
- Implement reasonable solutions for both PlanetyPlay survey system data as well as SGI DiBL data

The key areas that are on the roadmap are refinements to the survey system for improving data analysis and the data export flow for in-depth analysis and data sharing. As the MVP analytics module is further used for research on the first case studies, we expect that new feature requests will emerge that will enhance the Analytics Module at a later stage.

The flexible and agile approach we envisioned in [D2.1](#) and [D3.1](#) has been mostly successful as we have continuously involved partners in user requirements and shared data samples. However, we are still waiting for the data collection from the first cycles to complete, which will allow GREAT partners to seriously work with the data towards answering research questions, and then get further feedback in regards to how effective the Analytics module is. Based on this input further refinement and adjustments will be made.

2. Brief introduction to this deliverable

Research and innovation in the GREAT project will provide new insights into the role of the games industry and non-commercial creative practices in the EU for the benefit of society. It is important to stress that the analytics module is not a new product but rather a tool that can be used in the GREAT project, while also providing insights into what analytics will be useful for different stakeholders.

3. Overall objectives for WP3

This deliverable describes the third objective in WP3 that was outlined in [D3.1](#):

- 1) Repurposing existing platforms for policy-makers' needs that will be identified throughout the 5 cycles of WP4 (see [D4.1](#)).
- 2) Creating one game in DiBL or PlayMob for each of the case studies of WP2. At least one for each of the 5 cycles.
- 3) Gathering and visualising data from each case study for research and evaluation purposes (WP4 and WP5).

4. Agile methodology

As planned, we have used an agile methodology described in [D3.1](#) and [D3.3](#). Readers familiar with these deliverables will find that this section on Agile Methodology was already covered there.

It may be that the method is not quite as agile as the method and approach described in [D4.2](#). As agile development assumes lots of iterations based on practical learnings from released milestones. This is harder to do when there is a smaller user base and with our longer cycle/project driven feedback loop.

The experience from the cycles so far shows that the agile approach, where we emphasise adaptability, collaboration, and co-creation is critical because there are still many interconnected moving parts.

Figure 1: Shows the agile process

During the development of the MVP of the Analytics Module, we have followed the key principles described below. For example, we have involved different GREAT partners, and shared sample data and screenshots.

- *Iterative development:* Instead of planning the entire project upfront, Agile development allows for continuous iteration and improvement, where we constantly de-risk the project and incorporate the latest learnings.
- *Stakeholder collaboration & co-creation:* Agile encourages close collaboration between developers and stakeholders, including researchers, policy-makers, and end-users. Regular feedback from these stakeholders helps ensure that the project aligns with the intended goals.
- *Adaptability:* Agile embraces that requirements and priorities may change over time. Teams are encouraged to be flexible and responsive to these changes, adjusting their focus in each sprint as needed.
- *Cross-functional Teams:* Agile promotes the idea of self-organising, cross-functional teams that allows us to leverage the full GREAT consortium's skills and expertise.
- *Continuous delivery:* Agile emphasises delivering functional, tested components at the end of each sprint - typically in 2-3 weeks cycles. This ensures that progress is measurable and allows for the early identification of any issues that may arise. This is critical also to ensure collaboration and co-creation.
- *Regular reflection and improvement:* At the end of each sprint, the team reflects on what went well and what could be improved. This continuous feedback loop helps refine processes and enhances the overall efficiency of the development effort.

The agile praxis had challenges especially around navigating between different agendas with not always overlapping interests. In a commercial environment, the exact functional scope and detailed feature sets of products and services often evolve in a rapid, feedback loop driven process with a larger amount of active users. This contrasts with the cycle driven nature of the GREAT project, which requires more upfront assumptions about the needs of future stakeholders. So basically we had fewer iterations, and made more upfront assumptions, which is at odds with a traditional agile approach, where you try to make the least possible assumptions, and iterate quickly.

Additional challenges are listed below that will also be present in the remainder of the GREAT project.

- Collaboration with external stakeholders around specific domains, purposes and target groups where the tools need to fit.
- Defining, refining and documenting the research process put some extra requirements in terms of where to store data and GDPR sensitivity. There

were also some extra requirements in documenting and aligning the process with the GREAT project's 9-step methodology.

- Developing an overarching and standardised methodology that will work across multiple case studies and works after the project ends.
- Designing and creating specific case studies in the platforms, where some features are ready and others are still being developed and/or tested.
- Extending and repurposing the existing platforms to serve current and future needs better.

Overall, it's hard to understand the specific ways that an outside partner like a stakeholder might want to interact with the data, so it's difficult to define an interface that allows them to dissect this data (or produce a static report of sufficient polish). Or even make sure that the data that we can feasibly collect matches the level of insight that a stakeholder might want/expect.

We also work with a large number of partners who are constantly running new campaigns so we only have a few chances at the cycle level to improve, based on feedback from a few stakeholders.

Everything else we need to iterate based on internal feedback and the kind of scope and functionality that we think is needed and can be accomplished.

It is still too early to conclude on negative and positive practice in this regard. However, the agile approach is the only feasible approach with this degree of uncertainty anticipated in the project case studies cycles.

5. Technical specification of the Analytics Module

5.1 Overview

The flow of data can be broken down into six stages:

- Collection: Game clients take in data based on user actions (tagged based on its origin).
- Monitoring: The flow of incoming data from live games is presented for initial quality control.

- Sharing: Raw data is shared with GREAT project partners for analysis.
- Analysis: GREAT project partners perform bespoke analysis on the raw data to gain in depth insights.
- Archiving: The original raw data is archived for long term storage and availability.
- Publication: Analysis results are published beyond the GREAT project partners.

Figure 2: Shows the architecture or the analytics module.

Fundamentally, the Analytics Module is designed to collect data while adhering to legal and ethical standards and share this with partners in a common, lossless format to enable bespoke data analysis. No specific assumptions are made in how this data might be analysed or even whether all games/cycles may perform the same kind of analysis.

Survey and DiBL data never collected any personally identifiable information in the first place that needs to be anonymised. country/city data is not very granular. Even

when we in the survey save an IP address, we save it as a hash key, which can't be reversed.

A dashboard to monitor current PlanetPlay surveys and Serious Games Interactive DiBLs now exists, but its primary purpose is as a 'liveops' tool, to ensure that data is arriving as expected for new campaigns and to give a very high level summary of the results only. Note that Playmob Ltd has been acquired by PlanetPlay since 1.3.2024, and therefore PlanetPlay surveys replace those from Playmob.

The liveops dashboard primarily seeks to answer the following questions:

- Have anticipated surveys and DiBL games been launched?
- What volume of traffic are they bringing in?
- What regions/languages are popular (survey system)?
- How are individual surveys performing in terms of engagement and completion rates?
- Barring more detailed analysis, what is a high level distribution of how people are answering (survey system)?
- How can I get access to data for a specific set of surveys?
- Are Tinybird costs/resources being used within acceptable parameters (survey system)?

5.2 Infrastructure

PlanetPlay Survey System

The survey system collects data anonymously (without requiring an account or logging personally identifiable information) via a Next.js app and stores them using the managed Tinybird real-time data analytics provider (<https://tinybird.co>) in a Clickhouse database (open source type of database).

Significant use is made of the company Tinybird's hosted API endpoints and 'materialised views' to continuously aggregate data. This ensures fast access to data for the liveops dashboard, while still preserving the original data for further export and detailed processing/analysis.

Thanks to hosting Next.js on Amazon Web Services via OpenNext (deployed with SST (<https://sst.dev>)), survey data collected is highly cost efficient. Resource capacity does not have to be estimated and provisioned in advance, based on the amount of expected survey sessions from upcoming distributions by game publishers.

Serious Games Interactive's DiBL games

The analytics for DiBL is currently kept in the DiBL platform as it would provide limited value to re-create that in the GREAT project.

The LiveOps dashboard integration is brought to the shared platform to make it seamless for GREAT partners to have an easy overview of ongoing surveys across both systems.

5.3 Data Collection & Formats

PlanetPlay Survey System

Survey responses are grouped by sessions under a random session with a universally unique identifier (UUID). A session contains a number of other data fields, based on where the session originated from:

- survey start time in UTC
- a combination of the 'survey' (unique survey content identifier), 'source' (game studio/game that promoted a survey), 'distribution' (promotion method that was used e.g. 'ingame' or 'twitter') and 'variant' (if A/B testing was used)
- the language the survey as shown in (based on available localisations and their browser's language preference)
- the 'user agent' string from the browser
- a hash of their IP address (to identify repeated participation)

As a respondent fills out a survey, data is collected as 'answers' for a set of 'questions' tagged with the session ID and using additional IDs for the question and answer text used.

Questions may be multiple choice and data is sent after each question is answered. The dwell time in milliseconds for how long a question was up before the respondent replied is also available.

Additional 'events' are also logged under a session, e.g. when a survey is first loaded up, the initial engagement, as questions are shown and if a link at the end of the survey is followed. This allows engagement and completion rates to be calculated to measure the effectiveness of a survey to collect insights via a specific partner and distribution.

The answer and question UUIDs used to collect data under a session can be mapped back to human readable text by help of a lookup table, which is also provided when sharing raw data.

This then results in 5 output files that can be shared if raw data is requested:

1. sessions.csv
2. answers.csv
3. events.csv
4. question_text.csv (key)
5. answer_text.csv (key)

5.4 Data Sharing & In Depth Data Analysis

Publications and other dissemination of outcomes and insights from surveys and DiBL sessions will undoubtedly have custom analysis, visualisation and interpretation needs. Rather than recreating our own version of business intelligence or data visualisation tools, we assume that this will be performed by other GREAT project partners beyond PlanetPlay and SGI, using their own set of preferred tools.

Thus we will ensure that raw data is shared in a generic format that is compatible with a wide array of tools. As of June 2024, several export formats have been identified for summarised and full session data exports, without specifically catering to any tool specific file format.

For survey system data e.g., this would be both normalised CSV exports of the session, answers and events data sources, as well as a denormalized version in a single CSV file that contains one row per session. Ideally this format can serve as a starting point for other partners to perform their own analysis. Small adjustments can be made over time to the data sharing format or workflow.

5.5 LiveOps Dashboard Screenshots

Figure 3: LiveOps Dashboard - Survey activity

Survey LiveOps
Activity Answers Geo Data Costs Admin
env: production

Survey
gci_2

Source
Select...

Distribution
Select...

Variant
Select...

Reset Filters

Visit Survey

> gci_2

Select range Select range

Work In Progress

This section is currently in development. The export files are not yet in their final format and/or include only a subset of the sessions right now.

3 matching full session exports available as CSV files New Data Export

	gci_2 · highrez-smite · ingame	
completed	Exported Sun, Mar 17, 2024 10:02 PM UTC by Joost Schuur 100 rows (32 kB) in 1.2s	🗑️ 👁️ ⬇️
	gci_2 · highrez-smite	
completed	Exported Sun, Mar 17, 2024 9:47 PM UTC by Joost Schuur 100 rows (32 kB) in 1.3s	⬇️
	gci_2 · highrez-smite	
completed	Exported Sun, Mar 17, 2024 9:45 PM UTC by Joost Schuur 100 rows (32 kB) in 1.2s	⬇️

Figure 4: LiveOps Dashboard - Basic data download

Figure 5: LiveOps Dashboard - DiBL list (only selected sessions)

Figure 6: LiveOps Dashboard - Survey answer summary

Figure 7: LiveOps Dashboard - Resource cost summary/breakdown

Figure 8: LiveOps Dashboard - Survey geo breakdown

Figure 9: LiveOps Dashboard - Access management

6. Roadmap for Analytics Module

After creating a prototype to monitor early trial surveys runs, several areas of improvement were identified to refine how data is collected, monitored or shared. Additional use case requirements are needed before many of these items can be implemented:

- **Full session data export:** The current live-ops dashboard has limited abilities to share aggregate survey system data. Only recently did PlanetPlay begin to settle on a specific export format that could simplify bespoke data analysis needs by other GREAT partners. We expect to proceed with a manual or automated method to perform this kind of export from the liveops dashboard in the summer of 2024.
- **Improved liveops survey data segmentation:** After the initial trial run of surveys, several opportunities to improve how live data is previewed were identified. This includes grouping data by specific survey identifiers and filtering answer summaries by popular dimensions.

- **Data syncing to separate DB:** While Tinybird's storage costs are cheap, survey response data should be backed up in at least one other location for redundancy. A secondary database server may also simplify a dashboard driven, automated full session export.
- **Adapt to any survey system or DiBL updates:** Enhancements to either the survey system or DiBL engine may require smaller changes to how certain fields are shown on the liveops dashboard or exported. However, keeping in line with the un-opinionated philosophy of the data collection and dashboard (in terms of the impact on actual data analysis), these changes are expected to be minimal.
- **Outside access to liveops dashboard:** The liveops dashboard currently provides access to any survey or DiBL game listed for those that have an account. Should real-time access to individual games ever be needed, more refined access controls would be needed. While it is not clear if this is needed for the GREAT Project, PlanetPlay will likely want to develop this for its other partners and make it available as an option for the GREAT project too.
- **Updates to data sharing API for real time access:** Current API endpoints exist primarily to power the liveops dashboard. At least one project (UNDP) will have a public facing view of some of the data that may require small changes to those endpoints or new ones. A public facing, open access API for a wider audience is not anticipated at this point.
- **Long term data archival:** Once specific requirements have been identified on how raw datasets might be shared as part of publications, data segmented by cycle/project may also need to be archived in public locations such as a git repository for longer term access. This will likely be a manual process, assisted by helper scripts, as this may not occur frequently enough to be fully automated.

7. Progression on Tasks and Deliverables

Based on the timeplan defined in the grant agreement, we have specified below the work in [D3.1](#) that covers the whole of WP3. Below is the overview of the current D3.2 deliverable gantt chart. Overall the activities are on track although the long-term archiving task is not quite mature yet. We are also not that far in integrating learning analytics (LA) research into the solutions.

GANTT CHART WP3 TECHNICAL DEVELOPMENT											
				Jan '24	12	13	14	15	16	17	July '24
	LEAD	Wing	Support								18
D3.2 MVP Analytics Tools module											
Prototype LiveOps	PM	S GI		X							
Prototype DiBL Dashboard	S GI	PM		X							
Workshop 1: Integrating LA Research into GBL	DiPF	PM/S GI	UoB								
MVP DiBL Dashboard	S GI	PM				X					
API used in LiveOps	PM	S GI									
Workshop to evaluate usage in latest cycle	S GI	PM	All								
MVP LiveOps V1	PM	S GI	DiPF, UoB							X	
Workshop 2: Tailor Learning Activities Using DeLA	DiPF	PM/S GI	Z SI, FU, UoB								
Workshop 3: Data Visualization & Dashboard Customization	DiPF	PM/S GI	Z SI, FU, UoB								
MVP Data Pipeline (result data archival and sharing)	PM	S GI								X	
D3.2 READY	S GI	PM	DiPF, UoB								X

Table 1. GANTT chart of WP3 for D3.2

8. Quality Assurance Procedures

We use TypeScript to catch some problems within the development IDE. Code changes are reviewed via git pull requests by the technical lead and then tested by several other team members on a test environment before they are integrated into the production branch. A CI/CD step ensures that a new release builds properly before a deployment to production. Additionally, survey specific configuration data is validated to ensure that there are no inconsistencies (e.g. questions with no answers).

9. Roles, Responsibilities and Collaboration

Task Leader Analytics Module: PlayMob & PlanetPlay

Jude Ower, CEO, Playmob
 Joost Schuur, Technical Integration manager, PlayMob
 Sandro Oliveira, Technical Lead, PlanetPlay
 Richard Vignais, Head of Product, PlanetPlay

WP3 Leader and Supporting with DiBL data integration

Simon Egenfeldt-Nielsen, CEO Serious Games Interactive
 Martin Lund, CTO DiBL

Input on Use Case and Best-practice analytics

Researchers from the partners ZSI, UNIR, FU and UoB have and will be consulted on a regular basis to try out new formats, test exports and see that they fit with the workflow and tools they are used to working with.

10. Data Protection and Privacy

10.1. Data protection

We follow a number of best practices in this project. For example, the principles and guidelines that Open Worldwide Application Security Project (OWASP) have put in place contributed to and can be applied to data protection and privacy practices within web applications. Note that OWASP is an online community that produces freely available articles, methodologies, documentation, tools and technologies. The principles and guidelines are presented below:

1. Data collected by the Survey Tech system is never personally identifiable.
2. Least privilege roles approach - only a small technical team has direct access to the database systems that hold the data.
3. Testing and production use separate database environments.
4. Access to production environments (and the ability to generate further access) is only assigned as absolutely needed.
5. Access to third party tools (e.g. Tinybird) only available through permission-based, named (not shared) accounts (subject to their strict password policies etc).
6. When shared via an API with the dashboard e.g., authorisation is required by the API endpoint.
7. Access by outside partners is limited to only their relevant surveys and regulated by named accounts.
8. Public data is only ever made available for very tailored purposes (e.g. when creating a highly specific data panel for a public web page).

10.2. Data privacy

We follow the principles described in [D1.1](#) Quality Assurance Handbook, relating to collecting consent for participation but in general all data is anonymous on the platforms. For evaluation purposes, we may add a key so that we can connect a response in the platform with responses in other survey tools. As such the data will be pseudonymized, and participants will need to be informed.

10.3. Ethics

We have followed the principles laid out in [D1.1](#) Quality Assurance Handbook, in relation to research integrity and good research practice, 2)

Research ethics for the protection of research objects, and 3) Societal relevance and ethical acceptability of research and innovation outcomes.

The responsibility for the research ethics using the technology in this deliverable lies with the Academic Lead of each case study, as stated in deliverable [D4.2 GREAT Case Study Plan](#). This is an area that the technology partners will be guided by the Academic Partner to ensure the highest standards of ethics are adhered to.

11. Open Access, Open Research Data & IPR

In general, we will make as much material and data available as possible.

11.1. Open access to tools & games

- The proprietary platform from DiBL and Playmob remains the property of the partners that brought it into the projects.
- The project-specific material will be made publicly available.
- Any open source release would not get access to the GREAT Project's infrastructure used by our surveys. For example, this means that they would need to set up their own Tinybird workspace to collect data.

11.2. Open access data

- All data is fully anonymized, and will be available for open access.
- This access may not be live updating, and instead take the form of a data dump in a git repository.

12. Closing remarks

The current MVPs serve as a strong starting point but we still expect them to develop more as we get more insights from the current and future cycles. As described in [D3.1 Technical Specification](#) and [D2.1 Intervention Design](#), we still aim for a high degree of flexibility in the method, and the accompanying technical platforms. The current MVP should be seen as a list of features we have validated in the first pilot cycle and that can support at least cycles #2 and #3 but not encompassing all the adaptations we may need to make throughout the project. This depends on the requirements of the policy-maker stakeholders that will be participating and progressing forward. We may see specific requirements that are more project-specific or entirely new features from either policy-makers, domain experts, teachers, citizens or other stakeholders.

